

Intensity and Frequency of Anger is high in the Individuals within the Age Group of 18 To 40 Years.

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Abstract:

People indulge themselves in various aggressive behaviour leading to significant psychological dysfunctions. The present study assesses the intensity and frequency of the anger test retest method of reliability has been used and criteria validity is calculated for this scale. Anger is an emotion but can also be considered as a personality traits. Some people use their anger in a constructive way and some in a destructive way. This is a self-evaluation scale. This scale shows frequency and readiness of anger. Person can his / her anger level, readiness or intensity of anger on the basis of this Anger assessment rating scale. Every person has symptoms of anger but some have low intensity and some higher. A person can judge his/her anger peak through this scale. Higher intensity or readiness of anger can harm one's physical and mental capacity. So people should be aware about this scale and can try to control his /her anger. They can follow the anger management techniques and can reduce them anger intensity.

Introduction:

Anger assessment rating scale has been developed due to the concerns about increasing rate of aggression among people aggression is a behaviour whose immediate intent is to hurt someone else. A popular view about human aggression holds the idea that evolution has shaped humans to be basically selfish it is human nature to be aggressive and aggression mice in both inevitable and uncontrollable. Aggression in everyday life is very easy to observe it can be seen in school children punching and punching each other on the playground for street gangs fought over territory and bragging rights, road rage, domestic violence. Aggression can be triggered by a variety of factors. Some aggression is a result of mastery needs sometimes however perceived provocation such as threat to self-esteem can produce aggression. Many negative emotion or norms can also promote aggressive behaviour. To address the problem of aggression among people a number of rating scale have been developed in recent years that include items related to factor instigating aggression among people among these are the anger self-assessment tool, anger disorder scale, level of anger escalation. These scales have been developed primarily as screening the nature of aggression and all have demonstrated reliability and validity for this purpose.

The need for a brief rating scale that could be used to screen out the level of aggression among people was instrumental in the development of anger assessment rating scale. Anger assessment rating scale is self-evaluation scale as it shows frequency and readiness of anger. A person who achieves high score according to the scale is suffering from angry and chronic angry nature. According to a survey conducted in India it has been found that include

items related to factor instigating aggression among people among these are the anger self-assessment tool, anger disorder scale, level of anger escalation. These scales have been developed primarily as screening the nature of aggression and all have demonstrated reliability and validity for this purpose. The need for a brief rating scale that could be used to screen out the level of aggression among people was instrumental in the development of anger assessment rating scale. Anger assessment rating scale is self-evaluation scale as it shows frequency and readiness of anger. A person who achieves high score according to the scale is suffering from angry and chronic angry nature .According to a survey conducted in India it has been found that approximately 5% people in India population are suffering from anger hostility aggressive syndrome.

Materials and Method:

The sample consisted of 1000 subjects 100 each from Different cities of India (Delhi, Haryana, Bihar, Jharkhand, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Rajasthan, and Orissa) consisting of both males and females with an age range of 18 and above years. The data was collected(individual administration of protocols) from the communities (workplace, residential, college) using English /Hindi version of the questionnaire. Anger data sheet developed by the investigator provides information about the factors associated with anger type and anger style of expression were involved. It consists a total of 30 questions on 3 point scale (be it yes, sometimes and no) it has **six** categories namely **calm nature, ambivert nature, antipathetic nature, aggressive nature, angry nature and chronic angry nature.**

Data Analysis:

Test retest method and criteria validity

was used for checking reliability in a gap of 10 days in which reliability Coefficient came out to be 0.87.

Result:

A total of 1000 participants were taken for the study, the data was collected from different communities (workplace, residential, college)

Percentage of chart:

Grade level	Percentage
Calm Nature	2.5 %
Ambivert Nature	44 %
Antipathetic Nature	45 %
Aggressive Nature	4 %
Angry Nature	3 %
Chronic Angry Nature	1.5 %

from 10 different cities of India. It is found that 1.5 % of people fall in the chronic angry nature category. 44% of people fall in category of ambivert nature. 45% in antipathetic nature. 4% fall in aggressive nature category and rest 3% and 2.5% fall in angry nature and calm nature respectively.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The present work highlighted the presence of aggression among people. It has been seen that intensity and frequency of anger was high in 18 to 40 years and decreased or lowered the intensity after 40 years of age. There was no significant difference between males and females. Significant difference has been found in the occupation.

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